

ORGANIZATIONAL AND METHODOLOGICAL PRINCIPLES OF DEVELOPMENT OF ECOLOGICAL COMPETENCE IN STUDENTS

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Abstract In this article, the organizational and methodical foundations of the development of competence activities among students based on ecological education of general secondary schools are highlighted.

Key words: competence, knowledge, skills, qualifications, media resources, information and communication technologies.

Development of knowledge and skills related to environmental protection of general secondary school students in ecology, formation and development of their scientific outlook, ability to think logically, selfawareness potential, social life and to acquire the knowledge, skills and competences based on a competency-based approach necessary for them to continue their education. The main goal of the concept is to determine the development strategy and new system of approach in secondary general education schools. Environmental education based on the competence approach enables students to have independence, an active citizenship position, initiative, the ability to use media resources and information and communication technologies wisely in their activities, conscious choice of profession, healthy competition and general cultural awareness. forms skills [1]. This determines the organizational-methodical basis for the development of students' environmental competence. In order to choose methods in ecological education and to introduce them into the continuous national education system, it is necessary to identify, analyze and define the existing natural environment and the objects affecting it. If the legal basis of environmental education and the foreign and domestic policies of the state do not match, the need to apply certain methods in practice will disappear. The object of ecological sciences is natural or anthropogenically changed ecosystems, and the subject is their protection, rational use and restoration. The difference between the disciplines in the ecological system can be either the object or the subject, or both. In any case, ecological sciences examine various aspects of its three main research subjects - natural, social and natural-social phenomena, processes and situations (natural, economic, social, political, legal, spiritual-educational) should reflect. Only then will research become ecological.

The answer to the question of how to adapt environmental education and upbringing to the requirements of the times, the Law on Education of the Republic of Uzbekistan and the principles of continuity specified in the National Personnel Training Program is being found. Also, "implementation of the tasks defined in the Strategy of Actions on the five priority directions of the development of the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2017-2021, contributing to the solution of environmental problems in the territories of the republic with the introduction of the educational system, growing Adoption of the concept of development of environmental education in the Republic of Uzbekistan was also an important reality in order to increase ecological literacy of the coming young generation, to form and develop ecological consciousness and ecological culture, to effectively organize the process of environmental education and training [2]. Wide adoption of advanced pedagogical technologies, the introduction of a differentiated approach to education in accordance with the abilities and capabilities of children, as well as the creation of advanced pedagogical technologies, modern educational and methodological complexes, didactic development of the educational process provision is the basis for improving the education management system. This, in turn, is the responsibility of the leaders of the educational institution to organize the educational process on a scientific basis and design directions, as well as the non-traditional management activities, applying the world-class achievements and innovations of education, science, technology and technology. imposes various new tasks on positive problem solving. Competence describes the pedagogue's spiritual outlook, psychological-pedagogical and organizational technological potential, that is, the potential of his professional opportunities. According to V.P. Toporovsky, competence is the level of the pedagogue's understanding of management, his individual abilities and skills, his inclination to self-development and continuous independent education, his aspirations, as well as the educational process based on modern requirements. determined by management capabilities. The professional competence of the teacher is the level of their understanding of the organization and management of the educational process on a scientific basis, organization, research, management, pedagogical abilities and skills, self-development and continuous independent education. we can say that it is determined by the possibilities of organization, management and improvement of educational process activities [3]. Ecological competence is manifested in the education of a person's attitude towards ecosystems and responsibility towards it. Such an attitude is formed only as a result of a person's desire to realize the consequences of the negative impact on the ecosystems that he unknowingly and thoughtlessly caused and to eliminate such an impact. Environmental responsibility includes qualities such as

love for ecosystems, personal responsibility, conscientiousness, devotion to duty, and caution.

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